

Title:

OCR Edition: Correspondence on the Synchronous Oscillation Hypothesis (1996–2000): Letters to Crick, Koch, Singer, and Eckhorn

Overview:

This record provides OCR transcriptions of eight letters selected from the correspondence files (including Crick, Koch, Singer, Eckhorn, Grossberg, and Blake, among others) preserved by the late Tamotsu and Kazuko Sohmiya. The letters included in this collection were selected by Seiyu Sohmiya from among the surviving correspondence preserved by the late Tamotsu and Kazuko Sohmiya. The criterion for selection was whether the eight letters contained discussions directly related to the “Synchronous Oscillation hypothesis,” a central theme in the Somiyas’ research.

For the original scanned images, please refer to the corresponding image edition.

Editorial Policy:

1. Spelling errors

Spelling errors present in the original documents have been retained and marked with [sic]. Annotations have been added in notes where appropriate.

2. Typography and style

Typeface and formatting have been standardized for readability. The original layout, indentation, and spacing of the source documents and so on have not been strictly reproduced.

3. Handwritten text

Handwritten annotations and corrections present in the original documents have been transcribed and clearly identified as handwritten text.

4. Japanese passages and English translations

Japanese passages in the original documents are transcribed as they appear. English translations have been provided for all Japanese passages. Translations are intended to convey the meaning of the original text faithfully, though they are not strictly word-for-word renderings.

5. Other annotations

Editorial notes have been added where additional context is considered helpful for the reader. These are clearly distinguished from the original text.

6. OCR accuracy

The transcriptions are based on careful manual review of the scanned images. However, some characters, particularly in handwritten portions or degraded sections of the original documents, may be difficult to read with certainty. Uncertain readings are noted where applicable.

7. Privacy:

For privacy protection, selected personal information, including portions of addresses and telephone numbers, has been redacted in the scanned images. The same redactions are reflected in the OCR transcriptions.

Provenance:

The original documents are held by Seiyu Sohmiya.

Letter 1 (1996-02-21, to Crick, from T. & K. Sohmiya)

Dr. Tamotsu Sohmiya, [MASKED]
[MASKED], Nagoya [X], Japan

February 21, 1996

Dr. Francis Crick
Kieckhefer distinguished Research Professor
the Salk Institute for Biological Studies
San Diego, California
USA

Dear Dr. Crick,

We were deeply affected by reading your paper, "Why neuroscience may be able to explain consciousness" (Scientific American December 1995) and your book "The Astonishing Hypothesis; Japanese Transl." Specially [sic] , we were very surprised at your hypothesis that consciousness arises from synchronized oscillations in the cerebral cortex. We have also claimed from the experimental results on the Gestalt law of grouping that the concept of synchronized oscillations in the cerebral cortex is the most effective idea as a principle that may explain all mental activities from visual perception to consciousness (Sohmiya, 1976, 1980; Sohmiya & Sohmiya, 1976, 1986, 1995; Enclosed). We do not know your original paper on the hypothesis and desire earnestly to read it. So we would appreciate receiving a copy of the paper and other related papers.
Please send us them.

We are enclosing copies of our papers on synchronization in "strength of pattern"[sic].

- 1) Sohmiya, T. (1976) [Explanation of the Gestalt law of grouping in terms of synchronized oscillations in strength of pattern.] [Proceedings of the 40th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] Pp. 449-450.
 - 2) Sohmiya, T (1980) [Analysis of cerebral function in man by interaction between left and right visual systems.][Proceedings of the 44th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] Pp.187.
 - 3) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1976) [Fundamental[sic] study on pattern recognition by a new experimental method.] Nagoya: Maruzen, [English abstract]
 - 4) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1986) Periodicity of strength of pattern in binocular rivalry. Perceptual and Motor Skills, 62, 943-950.
 - 5) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1995) Explanation of illusory contours in terms of strength of pattern and its spread effect. Perceptual and Motor Skills, 81, 1003-1020.
- The relation between your 25 mS in synchronized neural firings (Fig. 17-1, Japanese translation) and our 5~7 S in strength of pattern (Fig 5-7 in Sohmiya & Sohmiya, 1976, Maruzen);

- Simultaneity or synchronism in different positions in space (Einstein) Simultaneity or synchronism in different parts in the cerebral cortex.
- Your severe criticism for psychology in "Thinking about the Brain" (Scientific American, September 1979) is quite right and we have studies always with our mind to it. So it will give us great pleasure to have your advice and comments on our papers.

Sincerely yours

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]

Tamotsu Sohmiya

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]

Kazuko Sohmiya

Note:

1. No reply from Crick to Letter 1 (dated 1996-02-21) has been confirmed.
2. A letter dated 1996-03-25 was received by Tamotsu Sohmiya from Koch.
3. Among the materials enclosed by Sohmiya, the following can be viewed online:

1) Sohmiya, T. (1976) [Explanation of the Gestalt law of grouping in terms of synchronized oscillations in strength of pattern.] [Proceedings of the 40th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] Pp. 449-450.

<https://zenodo.org/records/20533858>

<https://zenodo.org/records/20533060>

3) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1976) [Fundamental[sic] study on pattern recognition by a new experimental method.] Nagoya: Maruzen, [English abstract]

<https://zenodo.org/records/20565921>

4) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1986) Periodicity of strength of pattern in binocular rivalry. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 62, 943-950.

<https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1986.62.3.943>

5) Sohmiya, T., & Sohmiya, K. (1995) Explanation of illusory contours in terms of strength of pattern and its spread effect. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 81, 1003-1020.

<https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1995.81.3.1003>

Letter 2 (1996-04-09, to Koch, from T. Sohmiya)

Dr. Tamotsu Sohmiya, [MASKED]
[MASKED], Nagoya [MASKED], Japan Telefax (052) [MASKED]

April 9, 1996

Dr. Christof Koch
Professor
Computation and Neural Systems
California Institute of Technology
Division of Biology 139-74
Pasadena, California 91125

Dear Dr. Koch,

Thank you very much for sending me copies of your exciting papers on the brain activities. I am impressed with your conclusion that "if the internal code....., such a temporal code is independent of the detailed time-course of the external events that trigger the neuronal firing.'

Now I am interested in the following questions; 1) the relation between 40-hertz oscillation in neuronal firing and slow oscillation in vision such as figure-ground reversals and strength of pattern (P); According to Sohmiya (1982, 1983), there are two kinds of suppressions which reach a maximum at 5~20ms and about 100ms, respectively. 2) the relation between the former suppression and 40-hertz oscillation; 3) What is synchronism in different parts in the cerebral cortex?

I also wish you much success in your continuing pursuit of the issues.

[Handwriting]

Are we aware of neural activity in primary visual cortex? fills with splendid ideas !

Sincerely,

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]

Note:

Two letters from Koch to Sohmiya were found preserved in the files of the late Tamotsu Sohmiya and the late Kazuko Sohmiya. However, neither of these can be definitively identified as a reply from Koch to Letter 2.

Letter 3 (1996-04-24, to Singer, from T. Sohmiya)

Tamotsu Sohmiya [MASKED]
[MASKED], Nagoya[MASKED] Japan

April 24, 1996

Dr. Wolf Singer
Max-Planck-Institut fur[sic] Hirnforschung[sic]
Deutschordenstrasse 46,
60528 Frankfurt a.M.,
Germany

Dear Dr. Singer

Yesterday I read your article "Long-range synchronization of oscillatory light responses in the cat retina and lateral geniculate nucleus" and was greatly impressed with the results in which (1) oscillatory activity is often associated with the synchronization of spatially distributed responses, (2) the oscillatory responses are not phase-locked to the stimulus onset, (3) the occurrence of synchronization depends on global stimulus properties and so on. In 1976, as in our enclosed papers, we found that Gestalt law of grouping results from synchronization in "strength of pattern" of each part of a pattern. Since that time, we have been dying for neurophysiological data on global stimulus properties, especially Gestalt law of grouping so I feel your paper like an anticipated love. Of course, she was beautiful and wonder-ful.

I wish you much success in your continuing pursuit of the issues and you obtain Nobel prize.

(I would greatly appreciate receiving a copy of your article "Rev. Neurosci. 18,555-586 (1995) and any other papers on the same subject).

Sincerely,

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]
Tamotsu Sohmiya, Ph.D.

Note:

Two letters from Singer to Sohmiya were found preserved in the files of the late Tamotsu Sohmiya and the late Kazuko Sohmiya. The letter addressed to Sohmiya et al., dated 1997-07-31, is believed to be a reply to Letter 3 (dated 1996-04-24).

Letter 4 (1997-08-19, to Singer, from T. Sohmiya)

Dr. Tamotsu Sohmiya, [MASKED]
[MASKED], Nagoya [X] Japan

August 19, 1997

Prof. Wolf Singer
MAX PLANK INSTITUT
DEPERTMENT [sic] NEUROPHYSIOLOGY
D-60528 Frankfurt/M.
Deutschordenstrasse 46
Germany

Dear Prof. Singer,

Thank you so much for your kind letter and for sending me copies of your intriguing paper;

- Visual feature integration and the temporal correlation hypothesis. *Annu. Rev. Neurosci.* 18, 555-586 (1995).
- Development and plasticity of cortical processing architectures. *Science* 270, 758-764 (1995).
- Visuomotor integration is associated with zero time-lag synchronization among cortical areas. *Nature* 385, 157-161 (1997).
- Synchronization of oscillatory responses in visual cortex correlates with perception in interocular rivalry.

English is not my mother tongue and, in addition, I am very weak in it. So it is very difficult for me to understand your papers. Hence, every day I shall carry around one reprint of the above papers and read it again and again utilizing every odd moment. And I shall certainly feel greater and deeper respect for your work.

I believe that the concept of synchronization is the most effective idea as a principle which may characterize and explain all of mental activities in the human brain.

I wish you much much success.

With best regards,
Sincerely yours,

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]
Dr. Tamotsu Sohmiya

Note:

1. No reply from Singer corresponding to Letter 4 (dated 1997-08-19) has been confirmed.
2. The following manuscript received by Sohmiya was a revised version of the paper under submission to PNAS: Synchronization of oscillatory responses in visual cortex correlates with perception in interocular rivalry. This paper was subsequently published in PNAS on November 11, 1997.

Letter 5 (1998-03-12, to Singer, from T. Sohmiya)

SOHMIYA INSTITUTE OF PSYCHOLOGY

[MASKED]

Nagoya [MASKED]

Japan

March 12, 1998

Prof. Wolf Singer

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE

DEPARTMENT NEUROPHYSIOLOGY

D-60528 Frankfurt/M.

Deutschordenstr. 46

Germany.

Dear Prof. Singer,

I am enclosing a copy of our article "Synchronization, decrease in strength of pattern, illusory contours, and neon color effect". Now we are preparing for two papers, "Connection between synchronization of oscillatory activities[sic] at early stages and the last stage in the visual system" and "Patterns of cortical activity, degree of synchronization, binocular fusion, and binocular rivalry".

Enclosed is the former summary. The latter is a study that inferred degree of synchronization between the left- and right-eye images by 'strength of fusion' and then examined the relation between a pattern of cortical activity in the primary visual cortex and degree of synchronization.

I will send you them as soon as they are published

With best regards

sincerely yours

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]

Tamotsu Sohmiya, Ph.D.

Note:

1. No reply from Singer corresponding to Letter 5 (dated 1998-03-12) has been confirmed.
2. Synchronization, decrease in strength of pattern, illusory contours, and neon color effect
<https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1998.86.1.3>
3. Patterns of cortical activity, degree of synchronization, binocular fusion, and binocular rivalry
<https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1999.89.2.665>

Letter 6 (1999-12-23, to Eckhorn, from T. & K. Sohmiya)

T. and K. Sohmiya [sic] Telefax (052) [MASKED]
[MASKED]
Nagoya [MASKED]
JAPAN

December 23, 1999

PROF. DR. R. ECKHORN
PHILIPPS-UNIVERSITAT MARBURG
FACHBEREICH PHYSIK
AG ANGEWANDTE PHYSIK/NEUROPHYSIK
RENTHOF 7
D-35032 WARBURG[sic]/GERMANY

Dear. [sic] Professor Eckhorn

Thank you so much for sending us copies of your intriguing papers on synchronization. They produced a great impression on us. Especially, Neural Mechanisms of Visual Feature Binding ... 1999, touched us to the core.

We wanted to include our recent paper, Pattern of Cortical Activity, Degree of Synchronization ... 1999, This is the reason why we have waited so long mailing you our profound impresion[sic].

We deeply regret that we could not get your 1988 paper when we wrote the above article. As soon as there is an appropriate occasion we will certainly refer to your 1988 work.

We wish you much success in your continuing pursuit on the synchronization hypothesis.

Sincerely,

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]
Tamotsu Sohmiya
Kazuko Sohmiya

Note:

No reply from Eckhorn corresponding to Letter 6 has been confirmed.
Additionally, no letter from Sohmiya et al. requesting reprints from Eckhorn has been confirmed.

Letter 7 (1999-12-24, to Singer, from T. & K. Sohmiya)

T. and K. Sohmiya Telefax (052) [MASKED]
[MASKED]
Nagoya [MASKED]
JAPAN

December 24, 1999

Prof. Wolf Singer
Max Planck Institute
For Brain Research
Department Neurophysiology
Deutschordenstrasse 46, D-60528
Frankfurt/Main,
Germany

Dear Prof. Singer,

We are enclosing our recent paper, "Pattern of Cortical Activity ...1999".

Only quite recently we have learned through Dr. Mogi's essay that you visited Japan on the spring of 1999. We were very very sorry to miss you.

今年の春あなたが日本に来られたことを Dr. Mogi's essay で極く最近知りました。もしご来訪を知っておれば、何を置いても駆けつれた[sic]ものと、まことにまことに残念に思っております。

We were presented with Eckhorn et al's 1988 paper, Coherent Oscillations..., from Prof. Eckhorn. We would greatly appreciate copies of Gray and Singer's 1987 a and b; Soc Neurosci (abstr) 404. 3 and Neuroscience [Suppl] 22: 1301P.

Sincerely,

[Signature: Tamotsu Sohmiya]

Tamotsu Sohmiya
Kazuko Sohmiya

Note:

1. In response to Letter 7 (dated 1999-12-24), a reply was received from Singer in a letter dated 2000-01-21.
2. The English translation of the Japanese text is as follows:

I have recently learned through Dr. Mogi's essay that you visited Japan this past spring. Had I been aware of your visit at the time, I would have prioritized it above all else to meet with you. It is with the deepest regret that I missed the opportunity to welcome you.

Letter 8 (2000-01-21, to Koch, from T. & K. Sohmiya)

T. and K. Sohmiyas [sic]
Sohmiya Institute of Psychology
[MASKED]
Nagoya [MASKED]
JAPAN

January 21, 2000

Professor Cristof [sic] Koch
Computation and Neural Systems
California Institute of Technology
Division of Biology 139-74
PASADENA, CALIFORNIA 91125
USA

Dear Professor Cristof [sic] Koch,

Thank you very much for a copy of your recent paper, entitled "A model of saliency-based visual attention for rapid scene analysis" and two Xerox articles by Prof. Logothetis, which we found very interesting and useful as well.

Enclosed please find copies of our papers on form perception, including a copy of Sohmiya & Sohmiya (1968) paper.

Dear Prof. Shinsuke Shimojo: 以下の英訳よろしくお願ひ致します。

1. Saliency と Strength of pattern について

お手紙にありました your saliency と our pattern strength (P) の類似性は、両者 (同一のものを別方向から表現したもの) の goal への接近の証しであり、両者を結合することによって attention・consciousness により接近できると思っています。

C. Koch & S. Ullman, "Shifts in selective visual attention: Towards the underlying Neural circuitry; 1985" お送り頂ければ誠に幸いです。

2. Logothetis' flash suppression と our suppression method (flickering method) について。

名古屋の電気は60サイクル(Hz)です。したがって、左右両図形を発熱電球下で長時間観察しますと下図の①Conventional methodを使ったことになります。また左右両図形を蛍光灯下で長時間観察しますと②のLogothetis の flash method を使ったことになります。この場合のBinocular rivalry は後者の方の交替像がやや鮮明になるかと思いますが、左右の両図形とも、検討の対象となる「未知」のものであるという点で①と②は同一です。両者はいずれも「未知」のもので「未知」のものを探ろうとしています。これは落体実験で言いますと、未知の空気の抵抗を残したまま、比重の異なる紙・木・石等を落として重力の法則を見出そうとするのに似

ています。一方、③では未知のテストされる図形(TP)とテストする図形(SP)を左右に分離し、且つSPを短時間呈示することによってその抑制力を一定にしています。一定した抑制力で変動するpattern strengthを測定した。この点で、③は①②と異なり、①と②は類似しています。かくて、小さい図形の方が大きい図形よりも強いpattern性を示すという明瞭な図的特性は3では10分間1回の測定で簡単に且つ量的にはっきりと得られますが、①②では100年の苦闘後に、小さい方が大きいものより強いらしいという結果しか得られません。

30年以上、Suppression method の有用性を主張し続けてきましたがまだ誰も使いません。不思議です。

3. Logothetis has not discovered ... について

Pは明らかに秒単位で振動的変動を示しています。この事実から適当な実験法、刺激、そして「振動同期する対象」をあやまらなければ同期活動は必ずサル・ヒトにおいても神経生理学的 or 生化学的レベルでも見出されると信じています。

Sincerely,

[Signature: T and K Sohmiyas [sic]]

T. and K. Sohmiyas [sic]

Note:

1. No reply from Koch to Letter 8 has been confirmed.
2. The English translation of the Japanese text is as follows:

Dear Prof. Shinsuke Shimojo, please kindly find the English translation below.

1. Regarding "Saliency" and "Strength of pattern":

As you noted in your letter, the similarity between your concept of "saliency" and our "pattern strength (P)" demonstrates that both approaches are converging toward the same goal—representing the same phenomenon from different perspectives. I believe that by integrating these two concepts, we can achieve a closer and more comprehensive understanding of attention and consciousness.

(On a related note, I would be most grateful if you could kindly send me a copy of the following paper: C. Koch & S. Ullman, "Shifts in selective visual attention: Towards the underlying neural circuitry," 1985.)

2. Regarding Logothetis' flash suppression and our suppression method (flickering method):

The electrical grid in Nagoya operates at a frequency of 60 Hz. Consequently, observing both the left and right stimuli for an extended period under incandescent lighting effectively employs ① the Conventional Method shown in the figure below. Conversely, observing both stimuli under fluorescent lighting corresponds to ②

Logothetis' Flash Method. While the alternating percepts in binocular rivalry may appear somewhat clearer in the latter case, methods ① and ② are fundamentally identical in that both the left and right stimuli remain "unknown" variables under investigation. In both approaches, researchers attempt to explore the "unknown" using the "unknown."

To borrow an analogy from physics, this is akin to trying to discover the law of universal gravitation by dropping objects of different specific gravities—such as paper, wood, and stone—while leaving the unknown variable of air

resistance unresolved.

In contrast, our approach ③ separates the unknown "test pattern (TP)" from the "suppression pattern (SP)"

between the left and right eyes, and stabilizes the suppression force by presenting the SP only for a short duration. By employing this constant suppression force, we successfully measured the fluctuating pattern strength. In this crucial respect, method ③ fundamentally differs from methods ① and ②, whereas ① and ②

remain highly similar to each other. Consequently, distinct configurations, such as a smaller pattern exhibiting a stronger "pattern nature" than a larger one, can be easily and quantitatively demonstrated with method ③ in a single 10-minute measurement. In contrast, methods ① and ②—even after a century of academic struggle—can only yield a vague indication that smaller patterns might be stronger than larger ones.

Although I have consistently advocated for the utility of this suppression method for over thirty years, it has yet to be adopted by others. I find this truly perplexing.

3. Regarding "Logothetis has not discovered...":

Pattern strength (P) clearly exhibits oscillatory fluctuations on a scale of seconds. Based on this fact, I firmly believe that as long as one selects the appropriate experimental paradigms, stimuli, and "objects of synchronous oscillation," synchronous neural activity will inevitably be uncovered in both non-human primates and humans, at either the neurophysiological or biochemical level.

4. In his letter to Christof Koch, Tamotsu Sohmiya made an unusual request. Specifically, he asked Prof. Shinsuke Shimojo to explain the content of a passage written in Japanese to Koch. Tamotsu Sohmiya's research records contain information that may provide background for this seemingly abrupt request. A memoir dated July 6, 1998, includes the following entry:

"A reply letter from Shimojo regarding the paper I had sent stated that Koch would probably be interested. His papers were sent to me. After leaving the University of Tokyo, Shimojo applied for a faculty position at California Institute of Technology. Koch was one of the reviewers and reportedly asked whether he knew Sohmiya."

Although the letter from Prof. Shimojo referred to in this memoir has not been found among the surviving materials, this entry may provide a clue to understanding why Sohmiya made this unusual request in his letter to Koch.

The editors do not assert the historical accuracy of the events described in the memoir. This note is intended solely to document that Tamotsu Sohmiya recorded these events in his personal research notes.